

INFLUENCE OF INNOVATIVE IDEAS ON HUMAN PSYCHOLOGY IN TEACHING PAINTING TECHNIQUE THROUGH ART THERAPY

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ELSEVIER

Raxmatova Ikbolxon Inomjonovna

Teacher of Termiz State Pedagogical Institute

SHirinova Bahoroy Ikmatillo qizi

student of Termez State Pedagogical Institute

Abstract: In this article, innovative ideas, color classification, their influence on the human psyche, and the creation of works of art using various materials in contemporary visual art are discussed in this article. information, and at the same time, the use of art therapy as an important factor in the correction of mental problems, that is, the extensive use of painting, ceramics and other forms of art serve as factors in the formation of a healthy environment. information is highlighted.

Keywords: archaic paints, art, painting, art therapy, technology, innovation, ability, talent, development, creativity, profession, progress, factor, imagination, thinking, feature, craft, style.

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INTRODUCTION

If literature, art and culture live, the nation and the people, the whole humanity will live peacefully!

Sh. M. Mirziyoyev

In today's globalized society, the priority directions in the education system are to educate a well-rounded person, to work on new innovative ideas for the development of society, including the goal set before us of the stages of development in the history of painting and material technology, the world and thought. To develop the knowledge of analyzing the entire process of the works of great painters, to understand and define the work method using innovative methods, and to achieve this goal, it performs the tasks of forming theoretical knowledge, practical skills, a scientific methodical approach to artistic processes, and a creative worldview. It is known that visual art is very important in the history of mankind. Humanity was created in such a way that the first signs of fine art appeared in its life. It can be seen that there are many directions of fine art at the moment. At the same time, this article also provides information about innovative ideas in the creation of works of art using various materials in contemporary visual arts.

It has been known since ancient times that various herbs and natural substances were crushed and powdered and used as dyes. Today, there are watercolors, watercolors and tempera, gouache, acrylic, and aniline paints, which

are often prepared with the help of modern techniques, depending on the composition, with the help of a mixture of various chemicals.

The word watercolor is derived from the Italian word (aquarelle or aqua-tento), French (aquarelle), English (painting in water colors), that is, it means water-based painting. Usually, watercolor paints belong to the group of adhesive transparent paints. Glycyvirin, invert sugar and in some cases honey are added to these dyes as plasticizers. If it is done using this method, the quality of flexibility increases and melts faster, it creates more convenience in the process of operation. It is known that glycyvirine retains moisture for a long time, prevents paints from drying quickly and becoming brittle. A surface-active substance, bull gall bladder substance is added to watercolor paints. This creates an opportunity for light painting on paper. It can be seen that the substance of the bull's gall bladder does not allow the dyes to become droplets and accumulate. Antiseptic phenol is added to prevent the paint from becoming moldy. In the preparation of solid watercolors, their binders mainly include 3 substances. These include a mixture of gum arabic, dextrin and sugar paste. In the preparation of soft watercolors, a certain amount of gum arabic, dextrin and honey are added to its composition, taking into account the fact that it quickly dissolves in water. In other cases, glycerin is added to the honey background. This ensures the clarity of watercolor paint and quick dissolution in water.

The technique of working in watercolor goes back to the distant past. This is specifically mentioned in ancient Egyptian and Chinese manuscript sources. It was studied by artists of the Egyptian and Chinese school of miniatures in the Middle Ages and has reached the present time. The Gothic and Renaissance periods produced some great watercolor geniuses. Among them are the watercolorist brothers Limburg and Guberta Van Eyck, Jean Fouquet from France, Dürer from Germany. The great miniature artist Kamoliddin Behzod, the founder of the medieval Eastern school of miniatures, also created many miniature works in watercolor during his time.

These works have reached our time. After the invention of paper in the 2nd century AD, watercolor technique began to develop in China. By the 12th-13th centuries, the technique of working with watercolor paint moved to Europe. At that time, the watercolor technique had no meaning. In those times, watercolor paint was used only among other directions of painting. In the history of English fine art, the watercolor works of Guertin, Turner and Cotman were considered to be the national art of England.

Various paints were familiar to ancient Egyptian artists. They have come down to us through patterns made on papyrus. The origin of the binding agent of these paints is water-soluble vegetable glues. We can see this process in the

example of Persian miniatures. This method later spread to Eastern countries. By the 15th century, pure adhesive water paint (without additives) was used. These paints are distinguished by their purity and transparency. It is known from history that by the middle of the century, painters used gluey, water-soluble paints not only for the decoration of book covers, but also for paintings and artistic decorations.

In the West, the technical possibilities of paints were first widely disclosed by Albert Dürer. We can see this in the painter's scenic pictures. At the beginning of the 17th century, watercolor became an independent type of painting, and in the 18th century and precisely in the 19th century, it flourished thanks to the English painters and rose to a high level.

One of the mature scientists of his age, Newton studied colors from the point of view of physics, while the German poet and art critic I.V. Goethe was more interested in the effect of colors on the human body. Goethe divided colors into warm and cold types in his work "The Doctrine of Colors" and wrote that warm (yellow - red) colors evoke a mood in a person. By the 19th century, the German natural scientist G.L. Helmgols made an important innovation in the theory of color science. It can be seen that, based on many years of experience, it has been shown that chromatic colors should be classified on the basis of three main characteristics: hue, lightness and saturation.

It should be noted that Japanese scientists have always taken the study of color problems seriously. Even now, color, which is a natural phenomenon that affects humans, is studied on a scientific basis at the only Tokyo Color Institute in the world. The symbol representing the name of the colors, that is, the reason why one of them is called red, the second blue, the third purple, etc., is called a color tone. If we add a little gray to a chromatic color, its richness will decrease. This situation indicates the low saturation of the color, that is, the reduction of pure paint in its composition. So, by the saturation of a color, it is necessary to understand its level of color and purity compared to gray.

So, the issues of depicting real existence, life, and events with the help of paints on fabric, paper, board, and cardboard are mainly expressed in painting. Paintings are made in watercolor, watercolor, gouache, tempera and pastel. Art is truly a wonderful thing and it is truly therapeutic. By playing with words, music, paints, costumes, masks, clay and many other attributes of art, a person is able to create a hologram of an image, find the essence of a problem, art teaches survival and acceptance of life. it will Art heals, that is, it returns a person to wholeness, that is, to something spiritual, to his inner being.

Difference between art and other activities. The difference is that it does not set practical, pragmatic goals. In science, man strives for accuracy, correctness, to

understand the essence, to confirm it with various theories, and if art does not strive to create some formula, then art is holistic in its essence and at the same time imaginative, its fantasies, glitters with colors. Images and sounds cannot cause pain or injury, art can make a person feel and see the world in a completely different way, so he can feel himself and his experiences, evaluate himself differently. Each person has his own story. there is There are funny and sad moments in this story. There are also situations that you really want to remember, relive, maybe rethink.

One of the innovative ideas of our time is art therapy. Art heals: what is art therapy and who is it for? Art therapy can help heal emotions! Painting, dancing, pottery and other arts are used to correct mental problems: art therapy helps to overcome strong emotions and survive experiences that are difficult to express in words. For example, a suicide attempt. But not all psychotherapists recognize it as an independent school of therapy. Explores whether art can improve mental health, who does not qualify for art therapy, and how art can be used in conservative approaches to treatment.

Art therapy is the gentlest way to solve difficult problems. The child may not be able to talk or may not see his problems as his own. However, since creativity is in their blood, children sculpt, act and express themselves through their own characteristics. Also, art therapy sessions can relieve mental stress. In the past, our forefathers trained their children in trades and paid great attention to the important aspects of education.

In Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to the further development of culture, art and folk crafts, among all spheres of society. In our republic, treating spiritual values with respect, preserving and developing them, restoring national crafts, traditions, and priceless historical heritage has been raised to the level of state policy. PF-5242 Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on "Further Development of Handicrafts and All-round Support of Craftsmen" also provides for the complete preservation and reproduction of the rich cultural heritage and historical traditions of our nation, national crafts, people further development of artistic and applied arts, implementation of targeted and comprehensive measures for comprehensive support of citizens engaged in handicraft activities, on this basis, the population, especially young people, women and low-income families in order to ensure employment, a number of tasks that must be performed in the field of crafts have been defined. The knowledge given to young people about the fields of folk crafts serves the harmonious development of material culture and practical decorative art and helps to develop a number of qualities that are important for a person. This will help young people to learn, preserve and restore our national heritage and traditions, as well as get to know universal values.

Someone notices that you can create beautiful products from waste (branches, leaves, scraps of paper, sand, clay, stones). In addition, it is possible to solve a complex psychological problem - it is important to look at it not as before, but differently, new innovative ideas are being discovered. The human psyche is flexible. This feature gives you more customization. Later, children and adults undergoing art therapy can have hobbies, learn a new type of applied art. A new hobby allows you to focus more on yourself. This makes the relationship between parent and child more harmonious.

Stages of working with different materials (paper aging method using coffee):

1. The necessary paint (coffee) is prepared by mixing it with water in a special container, and it is applied to a piece of paper and tested.

2. When applying paint to the surface of the paper, the brush should always be dipped in the solution.

3. The next layer of paint is not laid until the paint on the bottom layer is dry.

4. The prepared special paint mass is applied to both sides of the paper and left to dry.

5. The edges of the dried paper are burned around to create an ancient look.

In this case, paper comes in the form of ancient manuscripts.

Paper selection. It is important to choose paper according to the work being done. Because there are different types of paper and they are designed for different purposes. For example, for working in pencil, dream, watercolor, etc. White dense paper is used for watercolor, and Watman, semi-Watman and Torshon papers are used for drawing. Such papers are easy to work with. Torshon paper holds paint better than smooth paper, and the colors shine more brightly in the light.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be noted that nowadays there are many directions of fine art, and innovative ideas in the creation of works of art using various materials are of great importance in contemporary fine art. The use of art therapy and the important aspects of art in directing the human psyche in a positive direction are felt. Work, craft and art, which is the fundamental basis of these, have a great role in the development of a person to the level of a human being. Emphasis is being placed on the implementation of new projects in the field of handicrafts, restoration and development of disappearing types of handicrafts. The accumulated experience in the development of modern society in the formation of art and craft culture with the help of art therapy from preschool age shows the need to preserve the national cultural heritage. It is worth noting that the republic has accumulated considerable experience in the restoration of traditional artistic culture over the past years. Projects related to the restoration and support of traditional art in Uzbekistan were considered as a state program. Serious measures have been taken for comprehensive development of all types of traditional art in the republic, relevant new structures have been established, and existing structures have been restructured.

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